

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN SOCIAL SOCIETY IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In this article, the conditions created for women and girls in the society and the opportunities created for them in order to increase their activity and their place in the society, as well as the conditions created by our country's president, were given information.

Key words: our life, law, history, women, affairs, council, deputy, queue, ancestors.

If we look not only at our current life, but also at history, we should pay attention to the glorious deeds of our great ancestors, who made an unforgettable and incomparable contribution to the development of humanity, brought them into the world, raised them with love.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miramonovich Mirziyoyev. President, at the special session of the Bukhara Regional Council of People's Deputies held on January 22, 2022, the flag of justice will be raised differently in districts with female leaders. "It's no secret that order, justice, honesty, and culture are high in places where women work and lead. That is why every ministry will appoint at least 1 female deputy in state companies, banks and other agencies within a year or two after training women in their system to be leaders.

In reality, a woman is the possessor of a delicate nature, kind, who thinks about everything right and wrong, good and bad sides, and has conscientious features. Of course, due to the development of our state and society and strengthening the role of women in its management, their role in society will increase. As a clear example of this, the achievements of our women in the world

Olympics; sportswoman, the most knowledgeable woman, people's leader, director, respected woman, scientist, writer, businesswomen, and in political life, the number of women senators, deputies, ministers, leaders is increasing. It is worth mentioning that, according to the research carried out in our country, women from low-income families included in the "Iron Book" and "Women's Book" have increased the number of grants for higher education and their entrepreneurial activities. It is important to increase the number of preferential interest-free loans and support them, which will help to make the promising society more stable and strong. Of course, it is the responsibility of women to bring up the future generation to be cultured and educated in all fields. Until recently, in our society, there were frequent misconceptions that "girls' education would bring the city, girls should think about getting married, not studying." But today, the political-legal, socio-economic image of our society is changing, new relationships are emerging in our lives, new values are being formed in the society regarding women's education. We are taking bold steps towards building the foundations of the Third Renaissance in New Uzbekistan. The New Renaissance depends, first of all, on the development of science and the strength of national spirituality. With a deep sense of this acute reality, it is necessary to mention that our state has introduced a package of

guarantees and privileges for women to get an education and engage in science, as well as creating new opportunities. ucation.

According to the decree of the President of March 7, 2022 "On measures to further accelerate work on the systematic support of families and women" in 2022-2026, women's economic, political and social life of the country the national program to increase its activity in all aspects and the comprehensive plan of measures aimed at the implementation of this program in 2022-2023 were approved. This certainly means that opportunities have been created for our women and girls to be educated and find their place in society. The great statesman Indira Gandhi said: "Educate one girl child, These words were not spoken in vain. Encouraging girls to be educated is an important step forward. Today's female student will become a mature specialist in her field tomorrow, as well as a mother who will raise a child with knowledge, intellectual potential, and a broad worldview. An enlightened woman makes a worthy contribution to making the right decisions related to the future both in her field and in her family. Every year in our country, February 11 is dedicated to the role and importance of women in the field of science. there is a symbolic meaning behind the holding of meetings, roundtable discussions, and events.you educate the whole family." In our country, comprehensive measures have been taken to support women engaged in scientific activities, to create scientific schools in scientific fields, and the national legislation in this regard has been improved based on the requirements of the times. In particular, the adoption of the Law "On Science and Scientific Activity" in 2019 serves as an important legal basis for improving the post-secondary education system. It is necessary to be careful. Gender equality is gaining importance in the development of society. As a result of paying special attention to increasing the activity of women and girls in the family, society, and in addition, in state administration, great changes are taking place both in social relations and in legislation.

It is noteworthy that in today's modernized society, due to the widespread involvement of women in politics and economy, certain changes, shifts, and even achievements in terms of gender equality are visible. In particular, Uzbekistan ranks 57th among 188 countries in the Gender Equality Index. This indicator is explained by the high level of education and economic activity of women. Or, according to the results of the parliamentary elections held in December 2019, the number of women in the national parliament reached 32% for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan. According to the "Women in National Parliaments" ranking of the Inter-Parliamentary Union, the Parliament of Uzbekistan took the 44th place among 193 countries. The share of women in political parties reached 46%, in higher education 47%. The ratio of women and men in leadership positions in the country was 27 percent and 73 percent, respectively. It is even more joyful that 16 of our honorable women received the title of "Hero of Uzbekistan", the highest award of our country, and 311 of our talented girls received the Zulfiya award.

The issues of using all the possibilities of folk pedagogy in educating our country perfect, morally pure, mature in all respects, devoted to their people and country, physically fit young people determine the purpose of studying this science. For example, it is important to explain the nature of national and spiritual values to the next generation. It is known that the people create values and transmit them from generation to generation. That is why values are widely studied pedagogically in law pedagogy, in which they are manifested in the following forms: family values, work values, values representing household life, values of socio-political content, cultural-educational values, artistic-aesthetic values. values, values

related to a healthy lifestyle, spiritual and spiritual values The aesthetic culture of society means the set of material and spiritual values accumulated in the entire history of human development. The aesthetic culture of the student's personality is formed as a result of active and creative assimilation of his cultural heritage.

The main components of personal culture are aesthetic consciousness, needs, attitudes and aesthetic activities. In order for teaching to be the same as in the brochure, students and pedagogues should have hygienic and physiological norms for their time in the classroom and at home. The main ways of planning optimization are carried out taking into account the teaching tasks, that is, the principle of approach to the design of the teaching and training process. These processes certainly help the development of the field of pedagogy. In our country, the teaching methodology of female pedagogues is increasing year by year, because attention to pedagogues in our country is increasing year by year. This shows that the education sector in our country will further develop in the future.

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